

Clients' Perception and Satisfaction with The Quality of Antiretroviral Therapy Services in Ekiti State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study determined the clients' perception and satisfaction with the quality of antiretroviral therapy services in Ekiti State, Nigeria. A prospective cross-sectional study design was carried out to yield quantitative data on clients' perception and satisfaction with the quality of ART services in Ado-Ekiti Local Government Area. The study targeted PLWHA who assess health care in Ado-Ekiti local government area. The sample size for the study was 400 PLWHA. Primary Data were collected using pre-tested and semi-structured questionnaires. The research assistants such as Nurses were trained to administer the questionnaire to ensure accuracy of the data obtained. The data obtained were analysed descriptively through descriptive statistics. The findings of this study revealed that the majority of HIV/AIDS clients in Ado-Ekiti local government area have a good perception about the services they receive. Similarly, almost all of them are satisfied with the quality ART services. It was recommended among others that it is important to establish a system of regularly getting clients' feedback on different aspects of the services provided, in order to improve on them and serve clients better.

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Introduction

The human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) and the resulting acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) was first observed in the early 1980s. Some decades later, HIV infection was increasing more rapidly in developing countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa. HIV/AIDS remains incurable and devastates many communities and nations. Since the first reported case in United States in 1981, it has spread to every country in the world. The ravages of the AIDS epidemic have made this disease the highest priority of our health system.

Nigeria has the second highest burden of HIV and AIDS in the world (UNAIDS, 2020). The general population survey in 2018 puts the country at an adult HIV prevalence of 1.9%. About 1.9 million people are estimated to be living with HIV/AIDS in Nigeria and the estimated number of new infections and HIV/AIDS related deaths was 130,000 and 53,000 respectively in 2018. Six states in Nigeria accounted for 41% of people living with HIV/AIDS (PLWHA) which include Oyo, Kano, Benue, Lagos, Kaduna and Akwa Ibom. The prevalence rate in rural areas is 4% while urban is 3%. Approximately 46,000 people died from HIV/AIDS related illness in 2019 in Nigeria. The prevalence of HIV in Ekiti State is 0.18% (UNAIDS, 2020).

Over the past decade, the rapid expansion of antiretroviral treatment in Africa and Asia has dramatically reduced HIV-related morbidity and mortality, and transformed HIV into a chronic illness (WHO, 2011). There are many antiretroviral treatment centres in hospitals across Nigeria that offers services ranging from diagnosis, staging, routine investigations treatment and routine follow-up. With all these, it still remains a challenge to achieve the universal access target of high quality of HIV/AIDS health care services and optimal patient satisfaction in many low-income countries with the hardest hit of HIV epidemics (Wolfe, Carrieri & Shepard, 2010). Patient satisfaction is defined as the patient's personal evaluation of providers' ability to successfully deliver care that meets patients' expectations and needs (Kagashe & Rwebangila, 2011)

Client satisfaction plays an important role in the assessment of health services quality used to establish institutional loyalty, usage patterns, word-of-mouth communications, and presumably to enhance the rate by which clients attain satisfactory levels of health. A number of factors influence patients' satisfaction with health care services including patients' socio demographic characteristics, physical health status, patients' personal understanding and expectations from various health care services that is, doctors, nurses, laboratory and pharmacy services (Kagashe & Rwebangila, 2011).

Hence, patient satisfaction with health care reflects the quality of services from the patients' perspective that supplements traditional indicators such as survival outcomes or processes of care (Crane, Lober, Webster, Harrington & Crane, 2007). In the same vein, the measurement of patient satisfaction could help health managers come up with measures to evaluate the performance of health care delivery system in addition to identifying patients in need of additional attentions or other interventions aimed at improving their health care (NACA, 2017).

Measuring patient satisfaction will enhance appropriate communication and building of stronger health worker-patient relationship based on identified gaps and barriers to effective performance of HIV/AIDS prevention and control programs from the patients' perspective. Although several studies have documented challenges with HIV/AIDS prevention and control programs in Nigeria (Olowookere, Fatiregun, Akinyemi, Bamgboye & Osagbemi, 2008), however what remains unknown is the magnitude and patterns of client satisfaction

and perception with anti-retroviral therapy services in health centres in Ekiti State, Nigeria that have different socioeconomic and cultural beliefs from areas where studies have been reported.

The general objective was to determine the clients' perception and satisfaction with the quality of antiretroviral therapy services in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The study specifically:

- i. assessed the clients' perception about the quality of services offered in Ado-Ekiti Local Government Area;
- ii. determined the clients' satisfaction with the quality services offered in Ado-Ekiti Local Government Area; and
- iii. assessed the quality of ART Services in Ado-Ekiti Local Government Area.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised for this study

1. What is the client's perception about the quality of services offered in Ado-Ekiti Local Government Area?
2. What is the client's level of satisfaction with the quality of services offered in Ado-Ekiti Local Government Area?
3. What is the quality of ART services in Ado-Ekiti Local Government Area?

Methodology

A prospective cross-sectional study design was carried out to yield quantitative data on clients' perception and satisfaction with the quality of ART services in Ado-Ekiti Local Government Area. The study targeted PLWHA who assess health care in Ado-Ekiti local government area. The sample size for the study was determined using the formula for calculating single proportion by Abrahamson and Gahlinger and after calculation, the sample size was 400 PLWHA.

There were 7 ART clinics in Ado-Ekiti Local government area (4 Governmental and 3 Non-governmental Clinics). Simple random sampling (balloting) method was used to select 2 out of each, making 4 ART centres. The number of clients that was chosen from each ART clinic was proportionate to the total population of clients in ART clinics. Simple random sampling method (balloting) was used to select an average number of clients that would be seen on each clinic day from each ART clinic entry point during the study period, and data was be obtained from the existing records.

Primary Data were collected using pre-tested and semi-structured questionnaires. These were administered to the eligible clients at the clinic. They were objectively designed to answer questions on clients' views regarding their satisfaction and perception of ART services in Ado-Ekiti Local Government Area. It consisted of four sections to cover the scope of the study. They are: Socio demographic data, Client's perception with service provision, Client's satisfaction with the service provision, and Quality of ART services.

The research assistants such as Nurses were trained to administer the questionnaire to ensure accuracy of the data obtained. The data obtained were analysed using the Statistic Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) where the research questions were answered descriptively through descriptive statistics.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the client's perception about the quality of services offered in Ado-Ekiti Local Government Area?

Table 1: Client's Perception about the service provision

Variable	Very poor	Poor	Average	Good	Very Good
Efficiency of service	2 (0.6%)	0 (0.0%)	11 (3.2%)	115(33.3%)	217(62.9%)
Friendliness of staff	2 (0.6%)	0(0.0%)	14 (4.1%)	120 (34.8%)	209(60.6%)
Helpfulness of staff	2(0.6%)	0(0.0%)	16(4.6%)	135(39.1%)	192((55.7%)
Cleanliness					
Nursing Station	4(1.2%)	0(0.0%)	7(2.0%)	124(35.9%)	210(60.9)
Waiting Room	3(0.9%)	4(1.2%)	9((2.6%)	115(33.3%)	214(62.0%)
Consulting room	3(0.9%)	1(0.3%)	11(3.2%)	77(22.3%)	253(73.3%)
Pharmacy room	3(0.9%)	1(0.3%)	9(2.6%)	127(36.8%)	205(59.4%)
Rest room	4(1.2%)	1(0.3%)	7(2.0%)	157(45.5%)	176(51.0%)

Table 1 shows that two hundred and seventeen respondents rate the efficiency of services at very good representing 62.9% of the total respondents. One hundred and fifteen respondents rate it at good equivalent to 33.3% of the total respondents. Eleven respondents rate the efficiency of services at average representing 3.2% of the total respondents, while two respondents rate it at very poor. Two hundred and nine respondents rate the friendliness of staff at very good representing 60.6% of the total respondents. One hundred and twenty respondents rate it at good equivalent to 34.8% of the total respondents. Fourteen respondents rate the friendliness of staff at average equivalent to 4.1% of the total respondents. Two respondents rate it at poor. One hundred and ninety two respondents rate the helpfulness of staff at very good representing 55.7% of the total respondents. One hundred and thirty five respondents rate it at good equivalent to 39.1% of the total respondents. Sixteen respondents rate the helpfulness of staff at average representing 4.6% of the total respondents while two respondents rate it at very poor.

Two hundred and ten respondents rate the cleanliness of the nursing station at very good representing 60.9% of the total respondents. One hundred and twenty four respondents rate it at good equivalent to 35.9% of the total respondents. Seven respondents rate the cleanliness of the nursing station at average representing 2.0% of the total respondents while four respondents rate it at very poor. Two hundred and fourteen respondents rate the cleanliness of the waiting room at very good representing 62.0% of the total respondents. One hundred and fifteen respondents rate it at good equivalent to 33.3% of the total respondents. Nine respondents rate the cleanliness of the waiting room average representing 2.6% of the total respondents while four and three respondents rate it at poor and very poor respectively.

Two hundred and fifty three respondents rate the cleanliness of the consulting room at very good representing 73.3% of the total respondents. Seventy seven respondents rate it at good equivalent to 22.3% of the total respondents. Eleven respondents rate the cleanliness of the consulting room at average representing 3.2% of the total respondents while one and three respondents rate it at poor and very poor respectively. Two hundred and five respondents rate the cleanliness of the pharmacy room at very good representing 59.4% of the total respondents. One hundred and twenty seven respondents rate it at good equivalent to 36.8% of the total respondents. Nine respondents rate the cleanliness of the pharmacy at

average representing 2.6% of the total respondents. One and three respondents rate it at poor and very poor respectively.

One hundred and seventy six respondents rate the cleanliness of the rest room at very good representing 51.0% of the total respondents. One hundred and fifty seven respondents rate it at good equivalent to 45.5% of the total respondents. Seven respondents rate the cleanliness of the rest room at average representing 2.0% of the total respondents while one and four respondents rate it at poor and very poor respectively.

Research Question 2: What is the client's level of satisfaction with the quality of services offered in Ado-Ekiti Local Government Area?

Table 2: Clients satisfaction with service provision

Variable	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Unsure/ Indifferent	Agree	Strongly Agree
It takes more than 30 minutes to get to the hospital	13(3.8%)	55(15.9%)	74(21.4%)	163(47.2%)	40(11.6%)
It takes more than the stated waiting period on the service carter to be served	4(1.2%)	40(11.6%)	199(57.7%)	95(27.5%)	7(2.0%)
It costs more than 100 naira to get to the hospital	8(2.3%)	19(5.5%)	53(15.4%)	208(60.3%)	57(16.5%)
The clinic is in good condition	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	7(2.0%)	159(46.1%)	179(51.9%)
The clinic is clean	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	9(2.6%)	179(51.9%)	157(45.5%)
I find the support groups useful	2(0.6%)	0(0.0%)	291(84.3%)	30(8.7%)	22(6.4%)
The toilets are dirty	35(10.1%)	240(69.6%)	47(13.6%)	17(4.9%)	6(1.7%)
I had to wait a long to get my folder	14(4.1%)	130(37.7%)	150(43.5%)	43(12.5%)	8(2.3%)
I had to wait a long to get my medications	12(3.5%)	63(18.0%)	158(45.8%)	106(30.7%)	7(2.0%)
There was a bench for me to sit on while I waited	4(1.2%)	8(2.3%)	76(22.0%)	212(61.4%)	45(13.0%)
The person who gave me my folder was helpful	0(0.0%)	2(0.6%)	22(6.4%)	265(76.8%)	56(16.2%)
The nurse who attended to me listened to my problems	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	17(4.9%)	222(64.3%)	106(30.7%)
The doctor who treated me was polite	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	19(5.5%)	191(55.4%)	135(39.1%)
I was pleased with the way I was handled at the clinic	0(0.0%)	2(0.6%)	13(3.8%)	209(60.6%)	121(35.1%)
The doctor explained to	2(0.6%)	2(0.6%)	9(2.6%)	201(58.3%)	131(38.0%)

me what was wrong with me					
My privacy was respected by all staff	2(0.6%)	0(0.0%)	14(4.1%)	226(65.5%)	103(29.9%)
I did not have to wait for long before I got my medicine	36(10.4%)	110(31.9%)	106(30.7%)	71(20.6%)	22(6.4%)
The staff visit at home to check on my improvement	280(81.2%)	39(11.3%)	14(4.1%)	7(2.0%)	5(1.4%)

Table 2 above shows that forty respondents strongly agree that it takes more than 30 minutes to get to the hospital representing 11.6% of the total respondents, meanwhile one hundred and sixty three respondents agree that it takes more than 30 minutes to get to the hospital. Seventy respondents are indifferent about it equivalent to 21.4% of the total respondents. Fifty five and thirteen respondents disagree and strongly disagree respectively. Fifty seven respondents strongly agree that it costs more than 100 naira to get to the hospital representing 16.5% of the total respondents. Two hundred and eight respondents agree to it equivalent to 60.3% of the total respondents. Fifty three respondents are indifferent about the cost of transportation representing 15.4% of the total respondents. Nineteen and eight respondents disagree and strongly disagree respectively.

Fifty two percent of the respondents strongly agree that the clinic is in good condition, 46% of the total respondents also agree whereas 2% of them are unsure while 45% of the respondents strongly agree that the clinic is clean. Fifty two percent of the total respondents also agree whereas 3% of them are unsure, 84% of the total respondents are unsure whether they find the support group useful. Though 9% and 6% of the respondents agree and strongly agree respectively. However 1% of the total respondents strongly disagree. Thirty five respondents strongly disagree that the toilets are dirty representing 10.1% of the total respondents. Two hundred and forty respondents also disagree, representing 69.6% of the total respondents. Forty seven respondents are indifferent about it.

Seventeen and six respondents however agree and strongly agree respectively that the toilets are dirty. Fourteen respondents strongly disagree that they wait for a long time before their folders are retrieved representing 4.1% of the total respondents. One hundred and thirty respondents also disagree that they wait for a long time before their folders are retrieved equivalent to 37.7% of the total respondents. One hundred and fifty respondents are indifferent about this, representing 43.5% of the total respondents. Forty three and eight respondents however agree and strongly agree respectively that they wait for a long time before their folders are retrieved. Twelve respondents strongly disagree that they wait for a long time to get their medications representing 3.5% of the total respondents. Sixty two respondents also disagree that they wait for a long time before their medications are dispensed equivalent to 18.0% of the total respondents. One hundred and fifty eight respondents are indifferent about it equivalent to 45.8% of the total respondents. One hundred and six, and seven respondents agree and strongly agree respectively that they wait for a long time before their medications are dispensed.

Two hundred and twelve respondents agree that there are benches for them to seat on while they wait representing 61.4% of the total respondents. Forty five respondents also strongly agree with this equivalent to 13.0% of the total respondents. Seventy six

respondents are indifferent about it representing 22.0% of the total respondents. Eight and four respondents however disagree and strongly disagree respectively that there are benches for them to seat. 77% of the total respondents agree that the person who gives them their folders is helpful. 16.0% of them also strongly agree that the person is helpful. 6.0% of the total respondents are unsure while 1.0% of the respondents disagree. 64.0% of the respondents agree that the nurses who attend to them listen to their problems. 31.0% of them also strongly agree to that. Only 5.0% of the respondents are unsure that the nurses listen to their problems. 55.0% of the total respondents agreed that the doctors who treated them were polite. 39.0% of them also strongly agreed that the doctors were polite. 6.0% of the respondents were unsure.

One hundred and twenty one respondents strongly agreed that they are pleased with the way they are handled at the clinic representing 35.1% of the total respondents. Two hundred and nine respondents also agreed that they are pleased, equivalent to 60.6% of the total respondents. Thirteen respondents were indifferent about it representing 3.8% of the total respondents. Two respondents however disagree. One hundred and thirty one respondents strongly agreed that the doctor explained what was wrong with them representing 38.0% of the total respondents. Two hundred and one respondents also agreed that the doctor explained what was wrong with them equivalent to 58.3% of the total respondents. Nine respondents were indifferent while two and two respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively.

Sixty-five percent of the total respondents agreed that their privacy is respected by all staff. 30.0% of the total respondents also strongly agreed that their privacy is respected by all. 4.0% of respondents are unsure, while 1.0% of them strongly disagreed. One hundred and ten respondents agreed that they wait for long before they got their medicine representing 31.9% of the total respondents. Thirty six respondents also strongly agreed that they wait for long before they got their medicine equivalent to 10.4% of the total respondents. One hundred and six respondents were unsure about this. Seventy one and twenty two respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed that they wait for long before they got their medicine. Two hundred and eighty respondents strongly disagree that the staff visit the clients at home to check on their improvements representing 81.2% of the total respondents. Thirty nine respondents disagree that the staff visit the clients at home equivalent to 11.3% of the total respondents. Fourteen respondents are indifferent, while seven and five respondents agree and strongly agree respectively that the staff visit them at home.

Research Question 3: What is the quality of ART services in Ado-Ekiti Local Government Area?

Table 3: Quality of ART Services

Variable	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Unsure/ Indifferent	Agree	Strongly Agree
My physical mental state improved after the visit of the doctor	4(1.2%)	0(0.0%)	5(1.4%)	166(48.1%)	170(49.3%)
I feel calm after the consultation	2(0.6%)	0(0.0%)	2(0.6%)	183(53.0%)	158(45.8%)
The doctor empathized with my situation	0(0.0%)	4(1.2%)	9(2.6%)	188(48.7%)	162(47.0%)
The doctor listened to me willingly and until the end	0(0.0%)	4(1.2%)	4(1.2%)	150(43.5%)	187(54.2%)

I know what how to prevent likely complications	0(0.0%)	2(0.6%)	23(6.7%)	140(40.6%)	178(51.6%)
I can always count on a solution if there are complications	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	10(2.9%)	165(47.8)	170(49.3)
A visit to the doctor usually results in an improvement in health	0(0.0%)	0(0.0%)	2(0.6%)	140(40.6%)	203(58.8%)
My doctor not only treats, but also gives advice on a healthy lifestyle	0(0.0%)	2(0.6%)	0(0.0%)	143(41.4%)	200(58.0%)

Table 3 depicts 49.0% of the total respondents strongly agree that their physical and mental state improved after a visit to the doctor. 48.0% of them also agree that their physical and mental state improved after a visit to the doctor. 2.0% of the respondents are unsure while the remaining 1.0% of the total respondents strongly disagree. One hundred and sixty two respondents strongly agree that the doctor empathizes with their situation representing 47.0% of the total respondents. One hundred and sixty eight respondents also agree that the doctor empathizes with their situation representing 48.7% of the total respondents. Nine respondents are indifferent equivalent to 2.6%. Four respondents disagree that the doctor empathizes with their situation equivalent to 1.2% of the total respondents.

Fifty-four percent of the total respondents strongly agree that the doctor listened to them willingly and until the end while 44.0% of the respondents also agree that the doctor listened to them. One percent of the respondents are unsure while another 1.0% of the respondents disagree, 49.0% of the total respondents strongly agree that they can always count on a solution if there are complications. Forty-eight percent of them also agree that they can always count on a solution if there are complications while 3.0% of the total respondents are unsure. 58.8% of the total respondents strongly agree that a visit to the doctor usually result to an improvement in health. 40.6% of the total respondents also agree that a visit to the doctor usually result to an improvement in health. 0.6% of the respondents are unsure. Fifty-eight percent of the total respondents strongly agree that the doctor does not only treat but gives advice on health lifestyle. 41.0% of the total respondents also agree that the doctor does not only treat but gives advice on healthy lifestyle. 1.0% of them however disagree.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that virtually all the respondents could vouch for the efficiency of the antiretroviral therapy services received. These services include: counselling and testing for HIV/AIDS, health education tailored towards prevention of new infections and healthy lifestyle, medical care of the clients, prevention of mother to child transmission, pharmacy services and client support at the hospital. Virtually all the respondents also found the staff in the ART clinics to be friendly and helpful to them. Doctors and nurses that attend to the HIV/AIDS patients are specially trained in the art of friendliness so that there should not be any form of stigmatization in the clinics.

The level of satisfaction and perception of clients regarding ART services was rated on Likert scale of very poor – very good from the matrix questions raised pertaining to the quality of services. Majority of the respondents (92.8%) are satisfied with the quality of ART services they received. In fact, 96.8% of them have a good perception about the services rendered to them. A similar trend was observed in a study done in South Africa that found

high levels of patient satisfaction with ART-related services in the public sector (Wouters, Heunis, Rensburg & Meulemans, 2008). This is inconsistent with results of a study done in Ethiopia, evaluating the quality of HIV/AIDS clinical care in a referral hospital. Although 78% of patients expressed satisfaction, the other 22% did not (Alemayehu, Bushen & Muluneh, 2009). This difference may be because clients in South Africa were satisfied with things like cleanliness of the facilities, yet in the current study, appearance of physical facilities scored very low.

Conclusions

Clients' perception and satisfaction is one of the imperative crucial components for success in healthcare service delivery. Principally, it is extremely more important and significant key issue in the ART units because of their vital role in the lives of hundreds of thousands of HIV/AIDS clients. The majority of HIV/AIDS clients in Ado-Ekiti local government area have a good perception about the services they receive. Similarly, almost all of them are satisfied with the quality ART services.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. It is important to establish a system of regularly getting clients' feedback on different aspects of the services provided, in order to improve on them and serve clients better.
2. The ART clinics should be supported to ensure a more constant and reliable drug supply for PLWHAS.
3. Close supervision of drug management is also necessary and staff can be trained in better drug management. All this will help to avoid the rise of ART-resistant viruses and reduce morbidity and mortality.

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